

STUDY OF NON-LINEAR TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON-EPOXY PREPREG COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Carbon fibre, epoxy, discontinuous*

1 Introduction

An important design limitation of high performance composites is the usual lack of any sign or warning before failure, which is often sudden and catastrophic with little or no residual load bearing capacity. To ensure safe operation, currently a much greater safety margin is applied for composites, than for more ductile materials such as aluminium or steel. These notable design limitations prevent engineers and operators from exploiting the outstanding strength of carbon fibre composites, letting them benefit only from the high modulus to weight ratio. They also render these materials unsuitable for many applications in which loading conditions are not fully predictable, and catastrophic failure cannot be tolerated. Given these limitations of currently available carbon composites, high performance materials that fail in a pseudo-ductile manner are of exceptional interest and could potentially offer a notable increase in the scope of applications including transportation and civil engineering fields. The study presented here is conducted within the framework of the High Performance Ductile Composite Technologies (HiPerDuCT) programme grant, with the final aim of introducing forms of pseudo-ductility into high performance fibre reinforced composites. Probably the most basic and straightforward strategy to achieve pseudo-ductility would be the incorporation of new ductile fibre types and matrices, but new materials need extensive and time consuming development and evaluation which is extremely challenging. Another option is to create controlled failure mechanisms by modification of the architecture of the composites made of commercially available materials, e.g. by introducing designed ply discontinuities. This

strategy offers scope for pseudo-ductility and is the topic of this conceptual design study.

The key challenge of the work to be presented is to develop a model system, which provides understanding of the factors controlling how failure propagates along ply interfaces and through the thickness of unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. This can be realized by the design of a suitable configuration which shows nonlinear stress-strain response with notable and detectable damage before failure, giving the possibility to control the failure of the specimens. Our most important objective was to exploit the high initial modulus of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy and the potentially nonlinear shear load transfer at layer interfaces. Some researchers have already used discontinuous ply composites for different purposes. Cui et al [1] executed central cut ply tests on UD glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy composite specimens and studied the delamination fracture energy of the specimens. The effect of layer thicknesses and through thickness stresses on the fracture energy and delamination stress in tensile and compressive setups was highlighted. Taketa et al [2] reported that applying designed slits in conventional prepregs can improve the formability of the material during hot pressing. This new approach can produce better material properties than the SMC (sheet moulding compound) hot pressing technology. Li et al [3] developed the so called unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) further by introducing new slit patterns to improve strength, material symmetry and flowability. Matthams and Clyne [4], [5] published a comprehensive study on the effect of laser-drilled holes on the tensile response of UD carbon/PEEK and carbon/PPS thermoplastic matrix composites. Various resulting fibre lengths in the range of 20-100 mm has been investigated, and no

decrease in elastic properties, but a modest drop in tensile strength have been reported. The original aim of the study was to improve the formability of the material, which has been assessed by applying significant strains during thermoforming and then tensile testing the UD composites. Deterioration of the structure, and drop in strength has been reported to be acceptable for up to 25% tensile strain during forming. Malkin [6] used cut ply prepreg to achieve a gradual and controlled failure in UD carbon plates under 4 point bending.

Our basic concept was different from those mentioned above: the use of discontinuous (cut) prepreg plies laid up in blocks and overlapped, to create a zone in the middle of tensile specimens, where the load has to be transferred by shear stresses on the ply block interfaces. Nonlinear stress-strain response is expected, as the load transferring interfaces encounter damage, and the stiffness of the overlap zone degrades significantly before final failure. The present study aims at showing a novel concept through a model system, which can be optimized later using different modelling approaches [7].

2 Preliminary calculations

During the design of a suitable model configuration for showing notable non-linearity in UD cut ply composite specimens, the basic criterion of pull-out before ply fracture is checked using formula (1).

$$\frac{mf\tau}{h-t} < \sigma_b \quad (1)$$

where m is the number of interfaces, f is the overlap length, h is the full thickness of the specimen (as shown on figure 1), t is the summed thickness of the cut plies, τ is the ultimate interfacial shear stress (between ply blocks) and σ_b is the fibre direction tensile strength of the plies. Equation (2) shows the analogous calculation of tensile stress in the continuous plies at (shear) failure σ_{cont} .

$$\frac{mf\tau}{h-t} = \sigma_{cont} \quad (2)$$

This simple criterion assumes a uniform distribution of shear stresses along the overlap areas, which is a notable simplification, but the equation is still applicable as a first check. The first specimen type

has been designed to be very safe against ply fracture. The following setup has been used: number of plies within a block: 8 except for the surface layers with only 2 plies. This reduction is necessary as the surface plies are much more susceptible to delamination. Firstly, there is only one delaminating interface for these blocks, effectively doubling the energy release rate. Secondly there is a mode I component which tries to “peel off” the surface layers. Reducing the surface ply block thickness from 8 to 2 plies should be sufficient to avoid premature delamination initiating there. Further parameters: ply block thickness: $t_b=1$ mm, full plate thickness: $h=5.5$ mm, full thickness of cut plies: $t=3$ mm, nominal overlap length: $f=4$ mm, number of interfaces: $m=6$, approximate interfacial strength $\tau=82.5$ MPa (from [8] for Hexcel’s IM7/8552 UD carbon prepreg). For the specified parameters, equation (2) gives an estimated maximum fibre direction stress $\sigma_{cont}=792$ MPa (in continuous plies at the most dangerous cross section), which is well below the tensile strength of the composite, even allowing for stress concentrations. This indicates that this setup is very likely to produce an interlaminar shear failure on the overlapped interfaces, without any layer fracture. The average stress across the whole thickness is only 360 MPa. A more realistic analytical model has been developed by Pimenta et al [9] that can take the local shear stress peaks around the ply cuts into account. These can initiate some local damage before the whole overlapped zone reaches its shear strength and goes unstable. According to this modeling study, another setup of ply block thickness: $t_b=0.25$ mm (2 plies, only 1 ply at the surfaces of the plate), full plate thickness: $h=1.5$ mm, full thickness of cut plies: $t=0.75$ mm, nominal overlap length: $f=7$ mm, number of interfaces: $m=6$ has also been investigated.

3 Experimental

A detailed description of the materials, specimen types, manufacturing, fabrication and test methods is given in this section.

3.2 Materials

Specimens were manufactured using IM7/8552 UD carbon/epoxy prepreg supplied by Hexcel Co. Ltd. with 0.125 mm cured ply thickness, 200 g/m² and 134 g/m² masses per unit area for prepreg and dry fibres respectively and 57.7% nominal fibre volume fraction. Hexcel 8552 is a toughened 180°C cure epoxy resin system and IM7 fibres are intermediate modulus carbon fibres with an elastic modulus of 276 GPa and strain to failure of 1.9%.

3.3 Specimen types and manufacturing

Two types of specimens with different geometrical parameters were tested in several series. This was necessary, because the novel manufacturing approach for the specimens, and the testing procedure needed some adjustments during the study. Figure 1 shows the geometrical parameters of the configuration selected for testing.

Fig. 1. Side view schematic to show the geometrical parameters of the discontinuous ply composite configuration tested in tension, where f is the overlap length, g is the gauge length for strain measurement, G is the free length and h is the overall thickness of the specimen. (Thick red lines show discontinuities.)

The nominal geometric values for the two different specimen types can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Geometric parameters of the specimen types tested (Both types had reduced thickness surface ply blocks, and 6 shear interfaces.)

	Nominal overlap length (f)	Gauge length (g)	Free length (G)	Overall thickn. (h)	Ply block thickn. (t_{block})
Specimen	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]
Type 1	4	7	8	5.5	1
Type 2	7	8.5	11	1.5	0.25

The steps of the manufacturing route for the novel cut blocked ply specimens were the following:

- 1 Cutting the uncured prepreg plies with a standard V-shape blade to the size of the plate to be manufactured.
- 2 Cutting the uncured prepreg plies with a 25 mm diameter rotary blade on a CNC ply cutter to create the overlap zone. Leaving 5-10 mm gaps between the edge of the cut plies, and in the middle helps to keep the plies in one piece and makes further steps easier. Figure 2 shows the perimeter cut (in red) and the internal cuts (in green) made during ply preparation steps 1-2.

Fig. 2. Geometry and cut pattern of the individual plies used for manufacturing of the cut blocked ply composite plates examined within the study (Red line shows the perimeter cut by standard V-shape blade, green lines show the cuts to create the overlapped zone, cut by rotary blade)

- 3 Laying up the ply blocks while carefully aligning one edge of the cut plies (preferably parallel to the internal cuts). It can be done by pushing the edges of the plies against a ground, prismatic piece of steel stuck on the bench.
- 4 Stacking the ply blocks together with the previously made cuts in the same way as in step 3. Particular care must be taken when aligning the cuts by turning every second ply block over to get the designed overlapped pattern shown on figure 1.
- 5 Bagging up the composite plate using a suitable size silicone frame around the composite to prevent extensive thinning of the plate towards the edges due to resin bleed-out. A rigid top plate (e.g. a 2-3 mm thick Al plate) was also necessary to prevent the composite plate thinning around the overlap zone.
- 6 Curing the composite laminate in an autoclave.
- 7 Fabrication of individual specimens with a diamond cutting wheel.

Figure 3 shows the resulting alignment of cuts on a typical longitudinal section micrograph for specimen type 1. It can be seen, that the alignment of the individual plies is not perfect, resulting in small steps within the vertical boundary of the resin pockets. The width of the resin pockets is around 0.5 mm and the resulting minimum overlap length is around 3.6 mm. Figure 4 shows a typical longitudinal section of the overlap zone of a type 2 specimen at a similar scale as that of figure 1 to enable visual assessment of the main differences between the geometrical setups of the specimen types tested within this study. It is clear from figures

3 and 4 that the resin pocket aspect ratio is changed significantly, and the resulting width of the pockets is almost 1 mm in the case of type 2 specimens. The measured minimum overlap length of type 2 specimens is 6.6 mm, almost twice as high as that of type 1 specimens. This parameter plays a key role in improving the failure stress and the nonlinearity in the stress-strain response. No explanation has been found for the increase in the resin pocket length despite butting the ply blocks with no gap during lay-up of both plates for the different specimen types. The resulting resin pocket dimensions probably depend on the local pressure and flow conditions inside the composite during the cure cycle, when the resin transforms into the liquid state and therefore cannot be controlled easily.

Fig. 3. Longitudinal section micrograph of a type 1 cut ply specimen

Fig. 4. Longitudinal section micrograph of a type 2 cut ply specimen

3.4 Testing procedure

Testing of cut blocked ply UD carbon/epoxy composite specimens was executed under uniaxial tensile loading and displacement control with a

crosshead speed of 0.2 mm/min on an Instron MJ6283 type 100 kN rated servo-hydraulic computer controlled universal test machine. Strains were measured using an Imetrum video gauge

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system with a Sony XCD-SX910 type CCD camera by tracking speckle patterns made by spray paints or paint markers on the specimen surfaces. Strain measurement has been done on one edge of the specimens. This was necessary, because we wanted to test the most rigid setup by reducing the free length of the specimens to the minimum to avoid excess strain energy stored in the continuous part of a longer specimen potentially making the specimens fail prematurely. The visibility of the specimen faces was blocked by the almost completely closed grip faces, therefore strain measurement had to be done on an edge of each specimen. Other strain measurement options such as clip gauge or strain gauges were not suitable because of the restricted space around the specimen (see figure 5).

Fig. 5. Type 1. cut blocked ply overlapped specimen in the grips

Please note, that the grip faces had 4 mm wide inclined sections each side where there was no contact to the specimen and therefore no gripping effect could take place. That is why the grips appear to be closed completely on figure 5 for a type 1 specimen test, where the nominal free length is the minimum achievable 8 mm. Good lighting conditions were crucial to make sure a good quality video could be obtained for strain measurements. Figure 6 shows the overall test setup with a high power studio light positioned overhead, because

this was the only possible way to get enough light in between the grip faces. An X-Y stage was used to move the fixed focus object-space telecentric lens mounted on the CCD camera to the right object distance for sharp, focused images. Details of the optical setup can be found on figure 7.

Fig. 6. Overall test setup for tension tests

Fig. 7. Videogauge camera setup with telecentric lens and X-Y stage

4 Results and discussion

Figure 8 shows typical tensile stress-strain curves of specimen type 1. Multiple curves appear on the graph because double targets were tracked during the tests to improve accuracy. The test curves have a notable scatter, because the displacements of the targets to be tracked by the videogauge system were very small due to the high stiffness and short gauge length of the specimens. Figure 8 shows two sets of curves because the resin pockets visible on figure 3 cracked at around half of the final failure load, causing a horizontal shift and change of stiffness of the specimens. This effect was highlighted by stopping the test at around the 80% of the failure load, unloading and loading the specimen up to final failure in a second run. Figure 9 shows the evidence for resin pocket cracking on an interrupted test specimen after applying a UV dye. The microscope image has been taken under UV light.

Fig. 8. Typical stress-strain curves of a type 1 specimen showing resin pocket failure in the first run

Figure 10 shows the individual stress-strain graphs of type 2 specimens. During the tests of this specimen type only one target was tracked as it was confirmed in the earlier series, that the discrepancies between strains obtained from multiple targets were acceptable and the lower thickness of these specimens indicated the use of a single target within the thickness. Strain data of this specimen type was much more stable due to the

lower specimen stiffness resulting in almost three times higher strains to failure than those of series 1. Please note that the curves of figures 8 and 10 show the responses of the overlap regions of the specimens only, as gauge lengths were set to be just a little bit higher than the overlap lengths, sufficient to allow a suitable area for the videogauge targets. Table 2. shows the summary of the test results of the different specimen types.

Fig. 9. Image taken under UV light of a type 1 specimen after an interrupted test and dye penetration (Green patches show the UV dye coming out of the resin pocket cracks.)

Fig. 10. Stress-strain graphs of type 2 specimens

The most important differences between the two specimen types are their different ply block thicknesses and overlap lengths which resulted in different failure types and stress-strain responses.

Table 2. Tensile test results of specimen types examined (terms in brackets indicate the coefficients of variation of the test data in %)

	Number of specimens tested	Actual overlap length (f)	Ply block thickness (t_{block})	Initial modulus	Failure stress	Strain to failure
Specimen	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[GPa]	[MPa]	[%]
Type 1	6	3.6	1	103 (8.8)	322 (3.2)	0.37 (8.7)
Type 2	3	6.6	0.25	122 (4.9)	1055 (1.2)	1.12 (3.3)

In a discontinuous ply UD composite specimen (see figure 1), where tensile load has to be transferred from one half to the other by shear on multiple interfaces within the overlap zone, two basic failure types are expected (assuming that fracture of the ply blocks is avoided by careful design):

- 1 The approximately uniform shear stress on the interfaces reaches the shear strength of the interface and the specimen fractures suddenly without any stable crack propagation.
- 2 Stable mode II crack propagation takes place before final failure of the specimen, reducing the load carrying area of the interfaces up to a point where the test goes unstable.

Type 1 specimens typically show the first type of failure because of the thick and therefore stiff ply blocks which do not extend enough to disturb the uniform shear stress distribution on the interfaces significantly. The short overlap length also helps to keep the variation of shear stresses down. Figure 11 shows the side views of the failed specimens. The average failure stress observed during the tests agrees well with the predictions given in section 2, especially if we take the actual overlap length of ~3.6 mm rather than the nominal value into account. The variation in the overlap length is due to manufacturing factors as resin pockets of ~0.5 mm width formed during the autoclave curing. The effective overlap length can be observed on the longitudinal-section micrographs of figure 3 and 4, being the shortest distance along the longitudinal axis between the corners of the two opposite resin pockets. An updated prediction for type 1 specimens using $f=3.6$ mm gives an average failure stress across the whole plate thickness of 324 MPa which is a very good estimation obtained from a basic model.

Type 2 specimens failed in another way showing significantly non-linear stress-strain response before final failure which is characteristic of the

second type of failure. The maximum stress and strain of this specimen type was significantly improved by the longer overlap lengths and the resulting much higher *total interface area/specimen cross sectional area* ratio, but the achievable maximum stress was limited by crack propagation.

Fig. 11. Edge views of failed type 1 (left) and 2 (right) specimens respectively

The lower ply block thickness (higher compliance) combined with longer overlap length resulted in significant displacements of the adjacent blocks around the resin pockets and therefore a non-uniform shear stress distribution along the overlap with peaks around the discontinuities. These stress peaks made relatively early damage formation and accumulation possible. As a result of the higher tensile stresses in the ply blocks due to higher shear

load transfer capacity of the longer overlap zone, the mode II energy release rate became high enough to drive delamination and the sufficiently long overlap length made it stable by providing enough residual load transfer capacity even after limited crack propagation. The average shear stress calculated on the initial total area of the six interfaces was only around half of the shear strength of the interface at final failure of the specimens. This suggests a significant reduction of load bearing capacity on the interfaces because of damage (reduced load transfer capacity) and/or crack propagation (reduced load transferring interface area) both rendering a notable part of the total interface inactive. The images taken for strain measurement purposes also indicate limited stable crack propagation before final failure. The non-uniform nature of the shear stress distribution, and the observed crack propagation before final failure invalidated the use of the average failure stress calculated with the simple tool of equation (2) for failure prediction in the case of this geometry.

In the case of both specimen types the specimens failed fully in the preferred way along the sheared interfaces and through the resin pockets showing no significant fibre fracture. In the case of thinner ply blocks of type 2 specimens, the resin pockets did not fail earlier than the final failure, or it was such a minor damage event that it was not detectable on the stress-strain graphs. A possible reason for this is that the longer overlaps of type 2 specimens combined with lower ply block thickness resulted in a negligible role of the relatively low stiffness resin pockets in tensile load transfer unlike in the case of the thick ply blocks of type 1 specimens. Basically the ratio of sheared interfaces, (loaded in mode II) to those loaded in mode I (on the transverse direction walls of the resin pockets) has been changed significantly. Overall, the lower ply block stiffness and the sufficiently high overlap length in the case of type 2 specimens made it possible to show significant nonlinearity due to progressive damage on the interfaces before sudden rupture in a material, which usually behaves linearly and fails explosively under UD tension if tested in a continuous fibre reinforced form.

5 Conclusions

- 1 A new manufacturing technique was developed for cut blocked ply unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates producing very well controlled discontinuous ply model specimens.
- 2 Two different specimen types were compared, and the second with 0.25 mm ply block thickness, and 6.6 mm overlap length showed significantly nonlinear stress-strain response before failure.
- 3 The reason for different stress-strain characteristics within the different specimen types was the difference in the ply block stiffness due to the thickness and variable overlap length. The thinner ply blocks and the higher overlap length of type 2 specimens resulted in higher stress and strain to final failure, because the total area of sheared interfaces was increased. The significant increase of strain to failure caused higher mode II energy release rate in the overlap zone allowing for crack propagation on the interfaces before final failure. The sufficiently long overlap zone provided enough residual load transfer capacity after crack initiation to make propagation stable for a limited extent.
- 4 A more favourable and controlled overall stress-strain response was shown for type 2 specimens compared to that of continuous UD composites which exhibit linear behaviour before sudden failure. Almost as high initial modulus was achieved as that of continuous fibre reinforced UD specimens. The reasonably high maximum stress (above 1000 MPa) was reached after a significant reduction in stiffness, which indicates progressive damage on the ply block interfaces before final failure. These results are even more notable, considering that the specimens had no continuous fibres between the grips.

Acknowledgement

This work was funded under the EPSRC Programme Grant EP/I02946X/1 on High Performance Ductile Composite Technology in collaboration with Imperial College, London.

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